

MEMORIAL MUSEUMS: DIGITAL CHALLENGES IN THE REPRESENTATION OF THE HOLOCAUST IN UKRAINE

Galyna Fesenko

Institute of Culture Studies of the Austrian Academy of Sciences

The “Artificial Intelligence (AI) Age” refers to the current era of rapid integration of artificial intelligence into all spheres of life, characterized by AI’s increasing capabilities in generating creative content, solving complex problems, and assisting in various fields. However, discussions are emerging about the future impact of AI, as well as the ethical implications that arise from it. Given the widespread use of digital media to access information about the past, AI is becoming an essential gatekeeper of historical information, determining which information sources are prioritized by platform algorithms (e.g., the Google search algorithm or the YouTube recommender algorithm). AI systems also determine the visibility of particular aspects of the historical event. To Europe as a whole, the Holocaust is also a symbol of the danger of aggressive nationalism and xenophobia, the rejection of democratic values, and human rights violations. How the Holocaust is portrayed on the internet, and particularly in social media, has a significant influence on the current and future

memory of the Holocaust and the Second World War. In particular, UNESCO's report "AI and the Holocaust: rewriting history? The impact of artificial intelligence on understanding the Holocaust" (2024) highlights such major concerns: AI models have produced misleading or false narratives about the Holocaust; deepfake technology can manipulate audio and video to fabricate Holocaust-related content; targeted campaigns by extremist online groups can exploit AI flaws to promote hate speech and antisemitic content about the Holocaust; some search engines and AI chatbots promote far-right content, including Holocaust denial; AI's tendency to focus on the most well-known aspects of the Holocaust oversimplifies its complexity. The omission of lesser-known episodes and events in the history of the Holocaust reinforces stereotypical representations of the Holocaust and its victims, and limits our understanding of a complex past that affected people in every country in Europe, and whose legacy continues to be felt worldwide.

It is crucial to ensure that digital progress does not obscure the authenticity and integrity of historical ideas, but rather enhances our understanding and interaction with the past. The use of images and textual elements of Holocaust history requires some curatorial moderation by the traditional custodians of historical knowledge, such as Holocaust Memorial Museums. They could offer extensive, carefully curated information on their websites and social media platforms, enabling them to confront distortion by acting as digital gatekeepers of historical truth and creating and promoting accurate online content.

They are able to develop and share engaging digital content, such as virtual tours, interactive videos, and online exhibitions, to reach a wider and more geographically dispersed audience, especially young people. However, the current museum activity needs to reflect on the potential impacts of AI on historical narratives and how to confront Holocaust distortion. Thus, they could help users to promote media literacy, critically evaluate online information, and recognize manipulation and misrepresentation of history. Memorial Museums also collaborate with research institutions and organizations, such as the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance (IHRA), to research and understand the subtle and emerging forms of distortion that appear online. This collaboration helps to create a common framework for documenting and monitoring incidents of distortion and developing effective countermeasures. They test and evaluate new digital tools and technologies, like augmented reality, to find innovative ways to make the history of the Holocaust more accessible and impactful in the AI space.

Since 2004, the recognition of the Holocaust as a common European history has become an informal condition for becoming an EU member state. For Ukraine, which gained the official status of an EU candidate in June 2022, the "Europeanization of memory" of the museum discourse on the Second World War and the Holocaust has become especially important. In Ukraine, there is still no National Holocaust Museum, although there are several local Holocaust museums established at the initiative of Jewish communities and with the support of local governments (in Dnipro, Odesa, Kharkiv, and other cities), as well as separate exhibitions at the "National Museum of the History of Ukraine in the Second World War. Memorial complex" and in regional museums. In Kyiv, the National Historical

and Cultural Reserve “Babyn Yar” has already been established, but public debate continues regarding the concepts of memorialization and in situ museumization. Some Ukrainian memorial sites are marked on the digital map “Memorial Museums” (<https://www.memorialmuseums.org>) on the information portal of the Foundation Memorial to the Murdered Jews of Europe (as part of the exhibition in the Information Centre under the Field of Stelae of the Memorial to the Murdered Jews of Europe (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Ukraine on the Information Portal “Memorial Museums”

For this study, an AI tool (ChatGPT) was used to analyse the “Ukraine” entry on this international portal in terms of its content, discursive framing, and potential impact on readers. The AI identified the text as a form of colonial discourse “about a region” rather than “about a nation.” Ukraine is often presented primarily as a problematic object with “dark chapters,” yet it lacks clear political agency. The narrative mentions that “nationalists attacked Jews,” that the “UPA killed Poles,” or that “antisemitism persisted,” but it provides little contextual explanation and fails to differentiate between historical groups, motives, and periods. Ukraine is depicted as a country that “began remembering victims too late,” “searched for its identity,” and “ignored the Holocaust,” which constructs an image of a passive and troubled space rather than a state capable of autonomous decision-making. In this narrative, Ukraine has almost no voice of its own, and its actions appear accidental or externally imposed—even after independence. Such framing shapes user perception: the discourse on Ukraine adopts colonial features, unintentionally reproducing elements of an imperial Russian narrative. Ukraine appears as a territory with a complex ethnic past but without a stable subjectivity.

This case demonstrates that AI can effectively reveal structural and discursive biases embedded in public information resources – biases that often go unnoticed in texts claiming neutrality, including those published by international scholarly and museum institutions. ChatGPT also generated a methodologically structured, academically appropriate synthesis of the full analytical process concerning the origin and validity of the figure “around 630,000 Jews”, used on the "Memorial Museums" international portal to describe Holocaust losses in Ukraine, demonstrates how digital

heritage platforms may unintentionally reproduce outdated or methodologically inconsistent statistical narratives.

The analysis, conducted through cross-referencing archival data, historiographical sources, and contemporary scholarly assessments, revealed a clear discrepancy between this number and the current academic consensus. At first glance, the number 630,000 appeared plausible because it has occasionally surfaced in historical literature. However, deeper analysis revealed that such references typically relate to partial datasets, most often: estimates of victims killed by Einsatzgruppen on certain sectors of the occupied Soviet territories, or limited territorial or administrative units within the USSR. Thus, the figure 630,000 does not represent all Jewish victims from the territories of present-day Ukraine.

Modern authoritative institutions, including the United States Holocaust Memorial Museum, Yahad-in-Unum, and major Holocaust researchers, estimate 1.2 to 1.6 million Jewish victims in the territories corresponding to present-day Ukraine. These numbers reflect: access to post-Soviet archives, regional studies of mass shooting sites, and contemporary demographic reconstructions. No recent scholarly work supports the estimate of “630,000” as comprehensive. The portal “Memorial Museums” provides no bibliographic reference for the number. No metadata, footnotes, or editorial documentation indicate that this is a primary source. Thus, the number “630,000 Jews” used on the Memorial Museums portal is not supported by contemporary authoritative research and does not correspond to the recognized historical scale of the Holocaust in Ukraine. Archival versions of the page (via the Wayback Machine) also contain no earlier attribution. This means that the number entered the portal without a transparent methodological grounding.

This approach to digital Holocaust representation is a common risk in digital memory platforms, where editorial processes are often non-transparent, and where numbers circulate without grounding in updated research. Its presence on an international educational platform underscores the urgent need for transparent sourcing, methodologically coherent statistical frameworks, regular scholarly review of digital heritage content, and the application of AI-based critical tools for verifying and contextualizing historical data. Through systematic cross-verification, AI tools help identify inconsistencies between public-facing narratives and current scholarship, trace possible sources of numerical distortion, expose implicit editorial biases (e.g., partial Soviet statistics still influencing Western platforms), and improve the accuracy of digital Holocaust historiography. In addition, AI-supported historical analysis can reveal hidden asymmetries, outdated data, and narrative distortions embedded in digital memory resources, even those produced by reputable institutions through systematic cross-verification.

Acknowledgements. The publication was prepared as part of the project “Ukrainian Memorial Museums: Exhibiting the Holocaust and war crimes in the context of an ongoing war and European memory culture”. This project has received funding through the MSCA4Ukraine project, which is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor

the MSCA4Ukraine Consortium, as a whole, nor any individual member institution of the MSCA4Ukraine Consortium can be held responsible for them.